

STUDIES ON THE REDUCTION OF DEHYDRODI-2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHYLMETHANE AND ITS DERIVATIVES

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The catalytic reduction of dehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane and its derivatives have been studied.

Dehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane, obtained by the mild alkaline oxidation of di-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane (I) (Abel, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 3477) was given the structure (II) by Pummerer and Cherbuliez (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2957) who showed that it gave a monophenylhydrazone and recognised its analogy with bimolecular dehydrophenols. A second structure (III) proposed by Kohn and Ostersetzer (*Monatsh.*, 1918, 39, 299) and

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

advocated by Dischendorfer (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 774; *Monatsh.*, 1927, 48, 543) was rejected by Shearing and Smiles (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1931) who supported the structure (II) and pointed out the inadequacy of the structure (III) in the light of the behaviour of the compound and the mechanism of its formation.

The significant characteristics of the structure (II) are the 1:2'-oxide linkage and the α : β -unsaturated ketone system. The presence of a double bond at 3:4 position was shown by Shearing and Smiles (*loc. cit.*) by the preparation of a dibromide which on treatment with pyridine loses hydrogen bromide giving 3-bromodehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane. More evidence of the correctness of the structure (II) has been obtained from a study of the behaviour of the compound and its derivatives towards catalytic hydrogenation.

Whilst reduction of the dehydromethane by zinc dust and acetic acid leads to the rupture of the 1:2'-oxide linkage giving (I) (Abel, *loc. cit.*), it has now been found that

catalytic hydrogenation in the presence of a mild catalyst, such as palladised barium sulphate (Pd, 5%), gives in addition the ketone (IV), characterised by the preparation of a semicarbazone. Hydrogenation with a more active catalyst, such as palladised charcoal (Pd, 30%), gave (I) as the main product together with a secondary alcohol (V, R=H), characterised as its benzoyl derivative. A poorer yield of (V, R=H) was obtained when Adams's catalyst was employed, the main product being again (I). The analogous catalytic reduction of 3-bromodehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane with a variety of catalysts led to the exclusive rupture of the oxide linkage giving 3-bromodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane.

Catalytic hydrogenation was next tried on (VI, R=H), prepared by Kohn and Ostersetzer (*loc. cit.*) by the action of methylmagnesium iodide on the dehydromethane. Whilst the compound is unaffected by zinc and acetic acid (Shearing and Smiles, *loc. cit.*), it has now been observed that catalytic hydrogenation leads to the quantitative reduction of the isolated double bond giving (V, R=CH₃) leaving the oxide link intact. Analogous reduction of (VI, R=Br) in the presence of Adams's catalyst gave the same product (V, R=CH₃) by the loss of the bromine atom as hydrogen bromide. The reduction of (VI, R=H) with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus in acetic acid proved very interesting as the molecule was cleaved with the formation of 1:2-dimethylnaphthalene (identified as its picrate) in poor yield.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Catalytic Reduction of Dehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane

(a) *With Palladised Barium Sulphate: Formation of spiro-(1:2)-2-ketotetralin- α' : β' -(2':1')-naphthodihydrofurane (IV).*—Dehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane (0.5 g.) in ethyl acetate (50 c.c.) was hydrogenated at room temperature and ordinary pressure in the presence of palladised barium sulphate (5% Pd, 3 g.). Hydrogenation was complete with the absorption of one molecular proportion of hydrogen. The solution was then filtered and the solvent removed in vacuum. The residue was dissolved in ether and freed from phenolic impurities by washing with 2% sodium hydroxide. Evaporation of the dried ethereal solution left (IV) as a gum which could not be crystallised. The *semicarbazone*, obtained by treating the gum with semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.5 g.) and excess of sodium acetate in alcohol on the water-bath, crystallised from butanol in colorless prisms (0.15 g.), m.p. 215-16° (decomp.). For analysis a sample was dried at 100°/15 mm.

over phosphorus pentoxide. (Found: C, 73.7; H, 5.3; N, 11.3. $C_{22}H_{15}O_2N_2$ requires C, 73.9; H, 5.3; N, 11.9 per cent).

(b) *With Palladised Charcoal: Formation of spiro-(1: α)-2-hydroxytetralin- α' : β' -(2':1')-naphthodihydrofurane (V, R=H).*—A suspension of dehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane (1.0 g.) in ethyl acetate (40 c.c.) was hydrogenated under similar conditions as in (a) above, in the presence of palladised charcoal (30% Pd, 0.2 g.). When the absorption was complete (1.3 molecular proportion), the solution was filtered and the solvent removed in vacuum. The neutral product (V, R=H) (0.2 g.) solidified in the presence of dilute alcohol and was obtained after two crystallisations from alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 143-45°. (Found: C, 83.3; H, 5.9. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 83.4; H, 5.9 per cent). It dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellow colour exhibiting intense green fluorescence. The benzoyl derivative was prepared by adding benzoyl chloride (0.2 g.) to a solution of the product (0.2 g.) in pyridine (2 c.c.) and leaving the mixture overnight. It crystallised from alcohol in colorless, hard prisms, m.p. 137-38°. (Found: C, 82.7; H, 5.4. $C_{24}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 82.7; H, 5.4 per cent).

(c) *With Adams's Catalyst.*—A suspension of dehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane (2.0 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) was hydrogenated under similar conditions in the presence of Adams's catalyst (0.1 g.). The absorption of hydrogen was complete in $\frac{1}{2}$ hour (1.1 molecular proportion) and the mixture when worked up gave (V, R=H) (50 mg.) and (I) (1.6 g.).

Catalytic Reduction of 3-Bromodehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane.—A solution of 3-bromodehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane (1.0 g.) (Shearing and Smiles, *loc. cit.*) in ethyl acetate (50 c.c.) was hydrogenated at room temperature and ordinary pressure in the presence of palladised charcoal (30% Pd, 0.2 g.). The hydrogenation was complete in an hour (1 molecular proportion) and the product when worked up gave the alkali-soluble 3-bromodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane (0.8 g.) crystallising from alcohol in colorless, felted needles, m.p. 202-204° (decomp.); Shearing and Smiles (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 201°. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 3.8. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2Br$ requires C, 66.5; H, 3.9 per cent). No neutral product was detected in this reduction.

Catalytic Reduction of (VI, R=H): Formation of spiro-(1: α)-2-methyl-2-hydroxytetralin- α' : β' -(2':1')-naphthodihydrofurane.—The compound (VI, R=H) (1.0 g.) was dissolved in pure alcohol (50 c.c.) and hydrogenated under ordinary conditions in the presence of Adams's catalyst (0.1 g.). After 45 minutes, one mol of hydrogen had been absorbed, and then the solution was filtered and concentrated when (V, R=CH₃, 0.9 g.) was obtained in colorless needles, m.p. 163-64°. (Found: C, 83.7; H, 6.4. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 83.6; H, 6.3 per cent). The product is insoluble in alkali.

Reduction of (VI, R=H) with Hydriodic Acid and Red Phosphorus.—A solution of the compound (VI, R=H, 5.0 g.) in acetic acid was refluxed with hydriodic acid (d 1.7, 30 c.c.) and red phosphorus (5.0 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The mixture was filtered, washed with acetic acid and the filtrate extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate and then with alkali. The alkaline extract on acidification gave a semi-solid product having the odour of β -naphthol, the presence of which was detected by diazo-couplings. The neutral product after the removal

of ether was purified by steam-distillation. The oily distillate was taken up with ether and distilled fractionally. The fraction distilling at 260° - 270° was converted into the picrate, crystallising from alcohol in orange needles, m.p. 125° , undepressed on admixture with the picrate of 1:2-dimethylnaphthalene, m.p. 130° . (Found: C, 55.4; H, 3.7; N, 11.1. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires C, 56.1; H, 3.9; N, 10.9 per cent).

Preparation of (VI, R=Br).—A solution of methylmagnesium iodide from methyl iodide (1.5 g.) and magnesium (0.25 g.) in ether was added dropwise to a stirred solution of 3-bromodehydrodi-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethane (3.0 g.) in benzene (40 c.c.). During the addition of the first few drops, the yellow colour of the solution seemed to deepen but immediately afterwards the colour began to fade away. The addition of the Grignard reagent was stopped when the solution became nearly colorless and after leaving at the ordinary temperature for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the product, when worked up in the usual way, gave a gum which crystallised slowly when left in contact with alcohol for sometime. It crystallised from aqueous alcohol in colorless, hard prisms (2.5 g.), m.p. 136 - 37° . (Found: C, 67.1; H, 4.5. $C_{22}H_{17}O_2Br$ requires C, 67.2; H, 4.3 per cent). The product is insoluble in alkali.

Catalytic Reduction of (VI, R=Br).—A solution of the bromo compound (VI, R=Br, 0.5 g.) in alcohol (30 c.c.) was hydrogenated in presence of Adams' catalyst (50 mg.). Approximately 1.8 molecular proportion of hydrogen was absorbed, the absorption towards the end being very sluggish (apparently due to the poisoning of the catalyst). The product, which was insoluble in alkali, crystallised from alcohol in colorless, felted needles, m.p. 159 - 62° , and was identical with (V, R=CH₃) by comparison and mixed m.p. (Found: C, 83.5; H, 6.3. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 83.6; H, 6.3 per cent). The product also gave negative Beilstein's test for halogen.

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